

Polarographic Study of the Composition and Stability Constants of Lead(II)-Ethylthioglycolate Complexes

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Complexation of lead by ethylthioglycolate has been studied polarographically. The reduction of lead in ethylthioglycolate solution has been found to be reversible and diffusion controlled involving two electron transfer process. Potential vs. concentration data at 0.5 M ionic strength were interpreted on the basis of the formation of three complex species PbA^+ , PbA_2 and PbA_3^- employing DeFord and Hume's method. The logarithms of stability constants of these complexes at 20° and 30° have been calculated and found to be 1.87, 4.39 and 6.40 at 20° and 2.0, 4.47 and 6.83 at 30° respectively.

Mercapto compounds containing an active -SH and -COOH group have a wide variety of applications varying from biological, pharmaceutical, analytical and other chemical uses and have been reported to form complexes with some metals and hence the importance of this class of compounds has grown. The polarographic behaviour of several such compounds, viz., thiomalic acid¹, β -mercaptopropionic acid², thiolactic acid³, and 3-mercapto-1, 2-propanediol⁴, and their metal complexes⁵⁻¹² have already been studied in these laboratories by Saxena and coworkers and yielded useful results. As a part of our earlier investigations, the complexation of ethylthioglycolate with lead (II) has been studied polarographically to determine the composition and stability constants of the complex ions formed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethylthioglycolate (ETG) was 97% Evan's Chemetics Inc., New York product. All other chemicals were Anal-R (B.D.H.) reagent grade and were used without further purification. Their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled air-free conductivity water. A solution of $NaClO_4$, 2.0 M, was used as supporting electrolyte and 0.1% Triton X-100 was used as maximum suppressor. All solutions used in polarographic measurements had, in addition to ethylthioglycolate, a lead ion concentration of 1.0 mM, 0.5 M $NaClO_4$ and 0.001% Triton X-100 in 40% ethanolic media at pH 10.5. The ETG concentration was varied from 0.02 M to 0.12 M. A Cambridge (general purpose) Polarograph in conjunction with thermostated H-cell was used for recording the current voltage curves. An external saturated calomel electrode was used as a reference electrode. The capillary used had the following characteristics: $m = 1.471$ mg/sec, $t = 3.52$ sec/drop ($h = 60$ cm) and $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.595$ $mg^{2/3}sec^{-1/2}$ at -0.72 V vs. S.C.E. The necessary correction for iR drop and residual current was applied in determining the half wave potential and diffusion current data respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} (height of mercury column after correction for 'back pressure') and i_d vs. concentration of Pb^{2+} was found to be linear indicating that the reduction was diffusion controlled. The temperature coefficient of i_d was found to be 1.60% per °C. All the reduction processes are reversible since, for any given polarogram, the slope of a plot of $\log i/(i_d-i)$ vs. voltage equals 0.032 ± 0.001 . The half wave potential values evaluated from the log plots for the current voltage of Pb^{2+} in varying ligand concentrations and the corresponding diffusion current values have been recorded in table 1. Half wave potentials were found to shift towards the more negative values with increasing ligand concentration, showing the complex-formation between Pb^{++} and ETG.

TABLE 1

Half-wave potentials, diffusion current and the values of the various functions at 20° and 30°

$C_x (M)$	$-E_1(V)$		$i_d (\mu A)$		$F_0(X) \times 10^{-3}$		$F_1(X) \times 10^{-4}$		$F_2(X) \times 10^{-5}$		$F_3(X) \times 10^{-6}$	
	20°	30°	20°	30°	20°	30°	20°	30°	20°	30°	20°	30°
0.00	0.720	0.720	4.35	6.20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.02	0.774	0.772	4.10	5.10	0.071	0.073	0.35	0.34	1.59	1.68	6.20	6.91
0.04	0.794	0.795	3.80	4.30	0.36	0.50	0.91	1.24	2.59	3.09	5.90	6.73
0.06	0.810	0.810	3.60	4.10	1.35	1.69	2.25	2.81	3.63	4.67	5.60	6.95
0.08	0.820	0.820	3.60	4.10	2.95	3.69	3.68	4.61	4.51	5.75	5.30	6.81
0.12	0.840	0.842	3.60	4.10	14.06	20.51	11.71	17.09	9.80	14.23	7.8	11.61

A plot of E_1 as a function of $\log [ETG]$ showed curvature expected from the formation of successive complexes. DeFord and Hume¹³ have derived a series of equations to relate polarographic data to complexity constants. For the reversible polarographic reduction of complexed metal ion to the metal amalgam

they have defined functions, $F_j(X)$, such that

$$F_0(X) = \text{anti log} \left\{ 0.435 \frac{nF}{RT} \times \left[(E_1)_s^0 - (E_1)_c^0 \right] + \log \frac{Is}{Ic} \right\} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$F_1(X) = [F_0(X) - K_0/fs] / C_x f_x \quad \dots (3)$$

$$F_2(X) = [F_1(X) - K_1/fm_x] / C_x f_x, \text{ etc.} \quad \dots (4)$$

$(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s^0$ and $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c^0$ are the half wave potentials for the uncomplexed and complexed metal ions respectively; I_s and I_c are the experimentally determined diffusion currents for

Fig. 1. Value of $F_0(X)$ and $F_1(X)$ for lead in ethylthioglycolate solutions (at 20°)
[(○), $F_0(X)$; (●) $F_1(X)$]

these species. K_0 the formation constant of zero complex is defined as unity. f_s and f_x are the activity coefficients of uncomplexed metal ion and complexing ligand respectively and C_x is the concentration of the ligand. K_1 is the formation constant of 1 : 1 complex and f_{m_x} , the activity coefficient of the complex. The intercept of a plot of $F_j(X)$ vs. $C_x f_x$, extrapolated to $C_x = 0$ is equal to K_j/f_{m_x} . Since the ionic strength is constant throughout

Fig. 2. Values of $F_2(X)$ and $F_3(X)$ for lead in ethylthioglycolate solutions (at 20°)
[(○), $F_2(X)$; (●) $F_3(X)$].

the investigation, the ionic atmosphere and hence the several activity coefficients probably change very little and one may equate them to unity¹⁴. Fig. 1 shows the plot of $F_0(X)$ and $F_1(X)$; and Fig. 2 the plot of $F_2(X)$ and $F_3(X)$ vs. ligand concentration. Extrapolation of these curves at $C_x f_x = 0$ gave values for the three formation constants as follows.

at 20° $K_1 = 0.70 \times 10^2$; $K_2 = 2.5 \times 10^4$ and $K_3 = 5.8 \times 10^6$

at 30° $K_1 = 1.00 \times 10^2$; $K_2 = 3.0 \times 10^4$ and $K_3 = 6.8 \times 10^6$

The plot of $F_3(X)$ (Fig. 2) showed a horizontal line which indicated that only three complexes were involved.

Thermodynamic functions : The values of thermodynamic functions viz., ΔG , ΔH and ΔS were calculated by the usual method and their values are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Stability constants and thermodynamic functions at 30°

Composition of complex M : L	Stability constant		ΔH (Kcal/mole)	ΔG (Kcal/mole)	ΔS (Cal/degree/ mole)
	20°	30°			
1.1	0.75×10^2	1.0×10^2	5.3	-2.8	27
1.2	2.50×10^4	3.0×10^4	3.2	-6.2	31
1.3	5.80×10^6	6.8×10^6	2.8	-9.5	41

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